

Motivation and Job Stress as correlates of Librarians' Time Management for Library and Information Services in South-South University Libraries, Nigeria

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Abstract

Introduction: This correlational study examined motivation and job stress as correlates of librarians' time management for library and information services in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria.

Method: The population of the study was 332 librarians in all the university libraries in the region, and no sampling technique was used as the population was manageable. Three experts validated the instruments (questionnaire): two from the Department of Library and Information Science and one from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation (Educational Foundation) at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Akwa. To establish the instrument's reliability, Cronbach Alpha was used to analyze the data collected from 20 librarians at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Library, resulting in a coefficient of 0.80. Pearson Product Moment Correlation and T-test correlation were used to analyze the research questions and test the hypothesis.

Results/Findings: Findings showed a low positive relationship between motivation and time management for library and information services delivery and a strong negative relationship between job stress and time management.

Conclusion: The study concludes that while motivation has a positive impact on time management, job stress negatively affects librarians' ability to manage their time effectively in university libraries.

Recommendations: University libraries need to invest in more programs and initiatives that will expedite library procedures and boost librarians' time management skills and efficiency.

Keywords: Motivation, Job Stress, Librarians, Time Management

Introduction

Time management involves planning and controlling the amount of time spent on specific tasks to work smarter, not harder. Several factors must be considered to boost productivity and work-life balance (Kashyap, 2019). Claessens, van Eerde, Rutte, and Roe (2017) define time

management as a wide variety of measures workers take to maximise their work time. Time management involves being aware of time, setting goals, prioritising tasks, and achieving goals. In order to succeed, library staff must learn to prioritise, organise, and delegate, as well as deliver library and information services under pressure. Time management skills are necessary

for library staff to perform their specific responsibilities in the growth and development of libraries.

Library employees need to minimise waste of time.. Many studies have shown that poor time management is harmful. Shah (2016) claims that spending time could result in poor service from Library employees. It may also lead to rage, annoyance, unhappiness, and library use decline. Lack of good time management is virtually usually the cause of work-related stress, job discontent, weariness, and other health difficulties. Poor time management has damaged professional relationships, degraded the library profession, and resulted in failure to fulfil deadlines (Macan, Shahani, Dipboye, and Phillips 2012). Evidently, poor time management can lead to missing deadlines, making work procedures burdensome, poor job quality, tarnished professional image, career termination, and increased anxiety and tension. With adequate time management, how can library employees provide successful library services?

Time management appears to be a crucial component of providing library and information services. However, experience has shown that some academic libraries' library staff are not time conscious and do not efficiently manage their time. Therefore, library staff must be diligent and time-conscious to deliver timely and efficient library and information services. If the reasons and determinants of poor time management among library staff are unknown, they cannot be improved. What factors and determinants affect library employees' time management? According to several studies, certain job activities can lead to poor time management. Misunderstandings consume time. It takes time to resolve misunderstandings, thus they waste time. Misperceptions about priorities, according to

Brian (2018), frequently result in library employees working at the wrong job, at the wrong time, for the wrong cause, and possibly at the incorrect quality. Ineffective delegation and vague job definitions waste time. Uncertainty about what is expected and a lack of skills may lead to time and resource waste. Poor time management failure can also be caused by a lack of foresight, an inability to prioritise, a lack of specific goals, a lack of motivation, an inability to accurately estimate time, and a lack of focus (Reid and Zyglidopoulos, 2004).

Thus, better time management by library staff can boost job efficiency and effectiveness with less effort. Efficiency means finding the best way to do something. However, efficiency involves evaluating several tasks, prioritising them, and completing them. Efficiency means doing the proper work, whereas effectiveness means doing the right thing, according to management. These two ideas drive time management solution acceptance. In order to maximise their time, librarians must choose and perform the most important tasks. Library staff have the opportunity to provide acceptable services within the expected and desired time frame with competent management; to improve service quality, minimise procrastination, and be more efficient and productive (Kashyap, 2019).

Users have long worried about quality academic library services, especially given the precarious state of our academic libraries, their employees, and our nation's economy. Alajmi and Alasousi (2018) found that academic library staff have struggled to deliver the desired information service due to low technology usage, incompetence, lack of technology knowledge, poor funding, and other issues. Poor library staff time management may hinder service delivery. Librarians have a time-consuming job.

According to Erdemi and Gozelii (2013), many complain about their lack of time for service delivery. Some university libraries want more time, yet few can manage their time properly even for modest library tasks (Ozdemir, 2006). What causes library staff time management variations?

According to Mohammadkarim et al. (2015) job stress, job satisfaction, and motivation may affect library employees' time management. Job stress is a medical condition in which workers' mental and physical health suffers as a result of their work-related activities and responsibilities being too much for them to handle (Peltzer, Shisana, Zuma, Van Wyk, and Zungu-Dirwayi, 2009). Over the past decade job stress and employee health have become major challenges, both nationally and globally. Some studies like that of Omol (2019) believe that reducing job stress could improve time management. Other studies found that proper time management eliminates job stress (Shah, 2016). Whatever the relationship, it is evident that job stress could be a predictor of time management of library staff. Job stress can cause anxiety, exhaustion, physical diseases, emotional problems, and even behavioral changes that would not allow for proper time management (Wengrzyn, 2021).

Furthermore, every day, employees face the challenge of staying motivated (Milliman, Gatling, and Kim, 2018; Riyanto, Endri, & Herlisha, 2021). When the necessary motivation is lacking, it is very difficult to get things done (Marketing 360, 2019). A lack of motivation makes it impossible to effectively manage one's time (Herzberg, 2007; Fitria Wiranti & Usman, 2021). To be successful in helping an employee manage their time, those library employees must be motivated as one of the initial actions (Zeller, 2016; Zeller, 2015). Therefore, it is possible that

motivation can be a factor to time management among library employees. The researcher wishes to explore time management in light of these contexts. Therefore, it is against these backgrounds that this study seeks to investigate the influence of motivation, and job stress on time management among library personnel.

Statement of the problem

Effective time management is essential for delivery of library and information services in university libraries. Librarians manage several tasks and ensure library services run well. Time management is crucial to productivity and service delivery, but librarians typically struggle with motivation and job stress, which can impair time management. In South-South, Nigeria, university libraries are key hubs for knowledge diffusion and academic support, therefore understanding motivation, job stress, and librarians' time management is crucial. However, this region's library dynamics especially as it relates to time management are rarely studied. This study bridges this gap by examining the relationships between motivation, job stress, and librarians' time management in South-South Nigerian university libraries.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to investigate motivation and job stress as correlates with librarians' time management for library and information services in university libraries in south-south, Nigeria.

The study specifically investigate the;

1. relationship between motivation and time management for library and information services delivery in universities libraries in South-South Nigeria.

2. relationship between job stress and time management for library and information services delivery in universities libraries in South-South Nigeria.

The objectives should have been

1. examine the time management strategies employed by librarians for library and information science delivery in South-South University Libraries, Nigeria
2. Identify the sources of job stress on the librarians in delivering library and information services in South-South University Libraries, Nigeria
3. determine the motivational factors that influence the librarians in delivering library and information services in South-South University Libraries, Nigeria

Research Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between Employees motivation and time management for effective service delivery in university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between job stress and time management for effective service delivery in university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Literature Review

Time management (TM)

Numerous scholars in different fields of study have defined time management (TM). It was defined by Osawe (2017) as the act of planning and arranging how to allocate time to complete specific tasks, objectives, and projects effectively and efficiently. Time management entails identifying and prioritising tasks, making objectives, developing timetables, and assigning

time to various activities (Bawaneh, 2015; Teng Zhi Peng and Akmal, 2017). This indicates that time management aims to enhance production and efficiency while decreasing stress and time spent. Rapp, Bachrach, and Rapp (2013) posit that time management (TM) is determining needs, setting goals, and prioritising and planning tasks to achieve organisational goals. A significant relationship has been established between job stress, TM variables, and employees' goal-setting, planning, and performance evaluation (Grissom, Loeb, and Mitani, 2015). The practice of utilising time efficiently to achieve maximum productivity includes controlling work schedules and engaging in prior planning, organising, and execution to accomplish organisational goals that are essential for the long-term survival of individuals and the organisation (McCune, 2011).

In addition, Mohammadkarim et al. (2015) and Bergman and Shubert (2013) had a similar definition of time management, indicating that time management is the process of managing time following the requirements of various assignments and activities to achieve long-term organisational success and maximise benefits by utilising, saving, and not wasting time or energy. Time management also refers to the approaches used to successfully manage (Farmer and Seers, 2014) and utilise time to complete different activities (NWOKA, 2022) via appropriate planning and allocation of time (Shah, 2016). It enables individuals to pursue planned and purposeful routes to obtain adequate knowledge to allocate time across many tasks effectively, maximising and enhancing intellectual production. Effective TM requires maximising productivity and performance via efficient time management. It involves planning, organising, and implementing work schedules in advance in order to fulfil organisational objectives. TM is a

crucial tool for both individuals and organisations, as it involves developing and deploying efficient techniques to accomplish projects within a specific timeframe and at the required quality level (Shehu, 2021). Within a job, it is human tendency to allocate time according to interest and comfort.

There is no definitive definition of time management. However, from the earlier definitions, time management can be contextually defined as the appropriate planning, organisation, and time allocation to suit library customers' needs. Time management is developing and implementing deliberate control over the time utilised for certain activities, primarily to increase effectiveness, performance, or output. Specific activities include establishing targets to meet needs or aspirations and organising necessary tasks. The process entails the prioritisation of tasks, establishment of goals, and execution of strategies to enhance service delivery. This ensures the prompt and efficient provision of library resources. As observed by Ebrahimi, Hosseinzadeh, Hosseinzadeh S., and Tefreshi (2014), workers spend their time on simple activities to maximise their time and organisation. However, appropriate time management is the only way to acquire the necessary skills and routines for professional success. It is a valuable tool for people and companies seeking to boost productivity and attain their objectives. However, it has disadvantages and restrictions. A possible advantage of time management is that it enables people to prioritise work and direct their efforts towards the most critical and urgent responsibilities (Mohammadkarim et al., 2015). This may result in enhanced efficiency and a feeling of success. Moreover, by developing calendars and establishing deadlines, time

management may assist employees in remaining organised and on track.

The collection of talents supports time management, means, and techniques needed to manage time while accomplishing specific tasks, activities, and goals with due dates (Kelling, 2018). According to contemporary sociologists, the method by which workers see time is tied to public issues, such as family relationships, gender responsibilities, and a person's workload (Mansour and Tremblay, 2016)—similarly, Ahmad, Mohd. Yusuf, Mohamed Shobri, and Wahab (2012) explained that in time management, individuals determine their needs and wants and then rank them according to their importance. Thus, time management is the efficient use of resources and a strategy for achieving personal ranked goals. In addition, time management is an efficient means of achieving happiness. Effective time management reduces the adverse effects of stress (Boyas and Wind, 2010; Eldelekiolu et al., 2010; Mohammadkarim et al., 2015).

Nonetheless, time management may have detrimental consequences. For instance, if library employees become too preoccupied with adhering to a rigorous schedule or achieving deadlines, they may neglect crucial activities such as leisure and socialisation. The inability to follow one's strategy may also increase stress and strain, ultimately leading to burnout (Reddy, 2016). Another disadvantage of time management is that it cannot be applied universally. Different work patterns may need different time management tactics (Arenas et al., 2018). Moreover, unanticipated occurrences or priority changes may derail even the best-laid plans.

This notwithstanding, time management may help enhance productivity and attain objectives,

but it also has disadvantages and restrictions. Time management is essential for library staff to run efficiently. The library personnel must manage competing time demands and be responsible for multiple tasks. They are responsible for ensuring the library is well-stocked and managed, that users are served quickly and effectively, and that library programmes and services run efficiently.

Effective time management for library staff includes identifying essential work, setting priorities, creating timetables and plans, and allocating time to tasks. It also requires responding to unexpected events and priorities. Library staff may have to prioritise tasks like categorising new resources, helping users research, and preparing events. For shelving, interlibrary loans, and the reference desk, they may need to schedule time (Cooperman, 2016).

The library experience is improved since patrons are served quickly and efficiently. Time management helps library personnel identify and prioritise tasks, set goals, create calendars, and allocate time to various tasks (The Library, Technological University of the Shannon, 2021). By identifying the most important jobs, library personnel may prioritise them. This ensures that the library runs efficiently and the most important jobs are completed on time. Gallia (2018) suggests that library personnel may benefit from making a timetable and setting due dates to stay organised. They may schedule time for categorising new resources, helping patrons research, and planning events. This ensures that all jobs are completed on time and that library programming and services function efficiently.

Pareto theory

Vilfredo Pareto proposed the Pareto Theory, also known as the 80/20 rule, in 1906. Pareto Theory

states that 80% of effects come from 20% of causes. This means that 20% of one's actions will produce 80% of his or her outcomes (Brock (2019; Kirillov, Tanatova, Vinichenko, and Makushkin, 2015). Time management is the most prevalent use of the Pareto Principle since most individuals choose to spread their time out rather than concentrate on the most critical activities. Workers may produce 80% of their job-related output in just 20% of their time at work (Odumeru, 2023). The Pareto Principle indicates that if you want to make the most of your time, you must understand that 20% of your activities and tasks are generally so crucial that they contribute 80% of the complete success of your job (Kirillov et al., 2015). For example, a librarian may realise he spends much time shelving books, answering reference inquiries, and responding to emails. Although these jobs are crucial to the library's operations, they may only partially contribute to its overall success or aims.

Applying this theory to the influence of occupational variables on time management means that a small number of occupational factors likely have a disproportionate impact on a library staff's ability to effectively manage their time. A workplace may have several initiatives and programs to create a positive and productive work environment (Plaut, 2016). However, the Pareto Principle suggests that 20% of these initiatives may have 80% of the impact on overall employee time management for service delivery (Bajaj, Garg, and Sethi, 2018).

In time management, the Pareto principle can be used to prioritise the most critical tasks and activities, ensuring that library staff time is used effectively and that the highest impact tasks, such as information Organisation and dissemination, are completed first. Regarding occupational variables, the Pareto principle can be used to

identify the 20% of job functions or responsibilities that contribute to 80% of a library staff's job satisfaction and success. By focusing on these critical areas, Library staff can improve their overall job performance and satisfaction.

Motivations and time management for library and information service delivery

Motivation is multifaceted and drives human behaviour and performance across areas. Motivation consists of many important aspects that work together to spark and sustain an internal drive in people (Alajmi & Alasousi, 2018). Motivated library employee is enthusiastic and energetic in their everyday tasks (Sahito and Vaisanen, 2017). The authors opined that they like new challenges and work positively. They take the initiative to improve systems, offer suggestions, and take on more duties to improve library services. Alajmi and Alasousi (2018) claimed that motivated library employees are dedicated to their duties. They pride themselves on providing excellent library services. Amida, Algarni, and Stupnisky (2020) say motivated employees develop objectives and strive towards them. They track and adapt their development.

A plethora of research studies have demonstrated that effective time management is a crucial factor in augmenting motivation and achieving a harmonious work-life balance. Through efficient time management, individuals can achieve a decrease in stress levels, an enhancement in intrinsic motivation, and an elevation in job satisfaction. However, only some studies focused on how motivation can impact time management skills. Motivation and time management are closely related in that they both play a crucial role in determining the success of Library staff in reaching their goals (Chaiet, 2021). Motivated library staff will have a clear purpose and direction for their efforts, making prioritising

their time and focusing on the most critical tasks easier.

On the other hand, Alajmi and Alasousi (2018) argued that practical time management skills could help individuals stay on track, reduce stress, and increase motivation by allowing them to focus on the most critical tasks. When motivation and time management are present, individuals are more likely to be productive, achieve their goals, and lead fulfilling lives (Zeller, 2016). Therefore, there is a symbiotic relationship between library staff's motivation and time management skills for information services delivery.

According to research examining the link between time management and motivation among university professors in Pakistan, workers with time management training had increased motivation, job satisfaction, and work-life balance (Sahito and Vaisanen, 2017). Time management enhances intrinsic motivation and work satisfaction by properly regulating and arranging a time to minimise stress (one of the essential elements in professional achievement) (Chaiet, 2021). Through goal-setting, prioritising, planning, and performance assessment, time management contributes to the motivation of workers. However, It is essential to note that these results may only apply to a specific group of Pakistani educators. The association between time management, motivation, and job satisfaction may be influenced by occupational contexts, cultural influences, and personality.

Motivation improves library staff time management, making them more productive, efficient, and focused (Yovina, Matondang, Sadalia, and Daulay, 2019). Prioritisation and other time management abilities are affected by library worker motivation. Prioritisation involves

prioritising tasks to maximise time and resources (Nguyen, 2020). When library staff are motivated, they have purpose and direction, making it easier to prioritise tasks. Yovina, Matondang, Sadalia, and Daulay (2019) report that this allows people to concentrate on the most important tasks and ensures that their time is well-used.

Motivation also boosts productivity, which helps employees manage their time (Flynn, 2011). When employees are motivated and engaged, they spend less time on irrelevant tasks and more time on goal-oriented tasks (Osabiya, 2015). This lets people finish tasks faster and better, freeing up time for other tasks. Motivation also helps workers focus (Wong, 2020). Focus is the ability to focus without distraction. The library staff's focus and time management depend on motivation. Motivated employees focus on tasks. Motivation gives employees a clear purpose and direction, helping them focus on the most important tasks and ignore distractions (Wong, 2020). Motivated employees may need problems focusing and are easily distracted, resulting in lower production and inefficient time utilisation.

Motivated employees are more involved in their task, which might help them focus longer. Motivated and inspired employees are less likely to burn out, which can help them focus for longer (Wong, 2020). Motivation affects focus and time management for library staff. Motivated employees are more focused, engaged, and productive, which improves time management and goal achievement. Motivated employees are less distracted and more focused on their tasks, which improves time management.

Motivation can improve library staff time management and service delivery, according to Jacques (2017). Efficiency is achieving goals with minimal waste, effort, or time. Efficiency of

library staff is frequently measured by their ability to perform tasks and meet patron needs in a timely manner. Motivation affects library staff's energy and focus, which affects time management. Staff are more productive and time-efficient when inspired and engaged (Aghaei, Habibi, Khodayari-Zarnaq, and Iraj, 2021). Staff members that want to provide outstanding service to patrons are more likely to prioritise their tasks and spend their time to help patrons. When employees are unmotivated, they may not prioritise tasks or organise their time well, decreasing efficiency.

Motivated employees are more productive, focused, and effective at their tasks, which helps them manage their time (Wong, 2020). However, unmotivated employees may procrastinate, suffer with time management, or be less productive (Hamid and Younus, 2021). Understanding motivation in time management and creating a motivating environment for library staff are crucial for library managers. Recognising and rewarding good work, offering professional growth, flexible work arrangements, and a healthy work culture help achieve this. The library can improve time management and guarantee staff can handle job demands by motivating and adapting staff.

Motivation also improves goal setting, a time management skill, according to Ogbeiw (2022). Project goals are SMART—specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound. Library personnel can better manage their time and prioritise tasks by defining clear and achievable goals. Goal-setting and time management require motivation. Motivated library personnel are more focused, productive, and goal-oriented. Motivated employees prioritise tasks that will help them reach their goals and maximise their

time. However, employees need greater motivation to set goals and manage their time.

Librarians must understand motivation in goal-setting and time management. By providing a friendly, motivating atmosphere, library managers may help workers set reasonable goals and manage their time. This can be achieved by promoting professional growth, rewarding good work, flexible work arrangements, and a healthy work atmosphere.

Job Stressors and Time Management

Work stressors are environmental elements or situations that cause an employee to experience emotional, psychological, or bodily stress. According to Bhui, Dinos, Galant-Mieczkowska, de Jongh, and Stansfeld (2016), job stress is a worry about performance that diminishes confidence and results in poor programme performance. Stress is any stimulation or change in the internal and external environment that may disturb the equilibrium of life and, under some conditions, be pathogenic (Leung, Liang, and Chan, 2017). Hence, stress is a person's need to adjust to physical, mental, and emotional change instead of the change itself. Stress is often related to limitations and requirements. It prevents the human's focus on his desires and refers to the absence of wanted objects. Mental and nervous pressure This is an everyday occurrence in today's workplaces.

Newton and Teo, 2013). Heavy workload, tight deadlines and time pressure, lack of job security, poor management and leadership, lack of control over work processes, unclear job expectations and roles, conflict with co-workers or supervisors, unfavourable workplace environment, work-life imbalance, harassment or discrimination are examples of typical job stressors in libraries: long hours, shift labour, and

a lack of acknowledgement and compensation for efforts.

Mata, Sohail, Haider, and Batista (2021) noted that job stress affects librarians' performance and results in poor delivery of library and information services. Changes in the internal and external environment disrupt the balance of life and may lead to sickness in some circumstances, causing stress which impacts the time management of library staff. Stress is often associated with demands and pressure. It hinders a person from caring about what is beneficial and leads to missing pertinent topics (Mansour and Tremblay, 2016). Beilock (2018) rightly observed that Employees at all institutions nowadays experience stress due to their psychological strain. The Yerkes-Dodson rule states that optimal performance occurs at a typical stress level. When the stress level is too high or too low, time management suffers. An individual's performance is at its peak when stress levels are normal.

According to Godard (2016), personnel conflict and dissatisfaction are critical causes of mental and physical exhaustion, early ageing and disease and their related effects. Although stress is unavoidable in the workplace and everyday life, people confront challenges, their performance and production decline, and they will suffer the repercussions. Increasing mental comfort in all organisations reduces tension and stress, increasing job productivity. Nowadays, work stress is one of the unavoidable concerns, and all cultures are experiencing stress. Since the job environment has different standards than the home environment, employees experience increased stress. For the progress and prosperity of a nation in all areas, the workforce must be in excellent health, vigilant, and creative. Using individuals with robust physical and mental

health in various businesses produces the most outstanding results. Extreme stress and anxiety are related to inefficient time management.

The literature evaluation conducted by Syaifuddin (2016) indicates that time management activities have a reasonable correlation with stress reduction and job performance. When library staff received instruction in time management, they demonstrated time management habits, although Macan (1996) does not support this. According to Macan (1996), time management training has little correlation with job stress or performance. By managing time, better library and information service delivery performances may be attained. The stresses are statistically connected with employee performance, indicating that an increase in these stressors decreases employee performance in service delivery. The variables of stress negatively and significantly impact staff performance.

Job stressors and time management may have sound and adverse effects on the delivery of library and information services (Claessens, Van Eerde, Rutte, and Roe, 2014). On the one hand, workplace stresses such as excessive workload, tight deadlines, and continuously shifting objectives may result in reduced productivity, an increase in mistakes, and a decline in job satisfaction among library employees (Mohajan, 2012). In contrast, strong time management skills such as prioritising, delegation, and intelligent scheduling may lessen the impact of occupational pressures and enhance the quality and efficiency of library and information services delivery.

Methodology

The research is a correlational research. A correlational design, according to Osuala (2005), defines the study's variables and their natural

relationship without the researcher altering either. This design is used because it can determine the variables' relationships. The need to elicit data to make inferences about the research population's occupational factors and time management for library and information service delivery made this approach suitable. This study was done at South-South Nigerian university libraries. Many reasons led to the study in south-south Nigeria.

The region has some of the largest university libraries. In order to provide information services and resources that support and enhance educational and research activities in institutions of higher learning, university libraries in the South-South region are crucial. There are 332 librarians in the South-south Nigerian university libraries. The survey sampled 332 librarians in South-South Nigeria university libraries. Pattern (2005) said that a census of every member of a small population is sufficient. So, the total enumeration method was utilised to count all librarians in South-south Nigerian university libraries. Three experts from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka's Departments of Library and Information Science and Measurement and Evaluation evaluated the questionnaire, the major study instrument. The instrument's reliability was determined by Cronbach's Alpha. To do this, 20 respondents at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, outside the study area, received study questionnaires. Cronbach statistics on SPSS yielded a coefficient of 0.82 for item internal consistency. The Pearson product-moment correlation answered research queries and the t-test correlation tested hypotheses.

Analysis of Research Question 1 and Hypothesis 1

services delivery in university libraries in South-South Nigeria?

What is the relationship between motivation and time management for library and information

Table 1: Pearson’s Correlation r on the relationship between work environment and time management for library and information services delivery in university libraries

Sources of Variation	N	Motivation r	Time management r	Remark
Motivation	318	1	.339	Low positive relationship
Time management	318	.339	1	

Table 4.7 displays the correlation between motivation and time management in university libraries for delivering library and information services. The Pearson correlation analysis in the table resulted in a correlation coefficient of .339. This implies a low positive relationship exists between motivation and time management for library and information services delivery.

Hypothesis 4

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between Employee motivation and time management for effective service delivery in university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Table 4.8. T-test correlation on the relationship between Employee motivation and time management for effective Service delivery in University Libraries

N	df	Cal. t	Correlation	P-value	Remark
318	317	3.382	.182	.001	Significant

According to Table 4.8, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 significance level since the calculated t 3.382 with a p-value of less than 0.05 has a df 317. This shows a significant relationship between employee motivation and

time management for effective service delivery in university libraries.

Analysis of Research Question 2 and Hypothesis 2

What is the relationship between job stressors and time management for library and information services delivery in university libraries in South-South Nigeria?

Table 2: Pearson’s Correlation r on the relationship between job stressors and time management for library and information services delivery in university libraries

Sources of Variation	N	job stressors r	Time management r	Remark
job stressors	318	1	-.771	High negative relationship
Time management	318	-.771	1	

Table 4.9 answers research question 5: What is the relationship between work environment and time management for library and information services delivery in university libraries? The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) between time management and job stress was -0.771 (p < .001). This suggests a strong negative relationship between the two variables. This implies that as

job stressors increase, time management decreases, and vice versa.

Hypothesis 5

Ho5: There is no significant relationship between job stress and time management for effective service delivery in university libraries in South-South Nigeria.

Table 4.8. T-test correlation on the relationship between job stress and time management for effective service delivery in university libraries

N	df	Cal. t	Correlation	P-value	Remark
318	317	7.943	-.473	.000	Significant

According to Table 4.8, the correlation between job stress and time management is -.473, indicating a negative but significant relationship. The t calculated is 7.943 with a degree of freedom of 317. Since the p-value is .000, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 0.05 significance level. This shows a significant relationship between job stress and time management for effective service delivery in university libraries.

university libraries. Although it is to a low extent, motivation impacts librarians' time management. Motivated employees are more focused and organised, which can increase their commitment to service delivery and performance (Alajmi & Alasousi, 2018). These findings support earlier research linking motivation and job satisfaction (Lee & Kim, 2016). Lee and Kim found that librarians exhibiting higher motivation levels were more inclined to acknowledge implementing effective time management strategies and delivering superior service to their patrons. Motivated employees are more likely to have good time management skills, which can boost job satisfaction and performance (Locke & Latham, 1990; Ola & Adeyemi, 2023).

Discussion

Relationship between motivation and time management

The study's findings showed a low positive relationship between motivation and time management for library and information services delivery. Analysis to test the corresponding hypothesis indicates a significant relationship between employee motivation and time management for effective service delivery in

This implies that employee motivation will improve time management, even to a low extent, which can boost service delivery and productivity. Thus, library administrators and managers should explore ways to motivate

employees, such as recognition, financial incentives, a good work environment, and professional development.

Relationship between job stressors and time management

The relationship between job stress and time management among university librarians in South-South Nigeria provides vital insights into the factors impacting employees' capacity to manage their time. The study's results showed a strong negative relationship between the two variables. This means that librarians' ability to manage their time decreases as job stress increases. These findings support Mata, Sohail, Haider, and Batista's (2021) results, which found significant negative correlations between time management and work stress. Similarly, Hashim, Jamaludin, and Zaini (2022) found that workload (job stress) and time management correlate significantly and negatively. Jamal (2017) discovered that job stress causes burnout, dissatisfaction, and poor performance. This shows that reducing librarian job stress will enhance time management and performance.

The hypothesis test shows a significant relationship between job stress and time management for university library service delivery. This suggests that librarians should address job stress to improve time management. The results also aligned with Hashim, Jamaludin, and Zaini's (2022) study findings. The authors found a significant positive relationship between time management and work-life balance. Library administrators and supervisors must help librarians manage their time by recognising and resolving sources of job stress and creating a healthy work-life balance.

Conclusion and Implications

This study has revealed the complex relationship between motivation, job stress, and time management among university librarians in South-South Nigeria, providing insights for improving library services and librarians' well-being. Motivation and time management for library and information services delivery were positively correlated but this correlation was low. The low correlation emphasises the need to motivate librarians to improve time management. Motivated employees focus and organise better, improving service and performance. Motivation, job satisfaction, and time management are linked, as shown by previous study. The study also found a strong negative correlation between job stress and time management, suggesting that librarians' time management skills have been hindered by stress. Addressing job pressures improves time management and employee well-being. Library managers should prioritise job stress reduction to provide a supportive work environment for time management.

The implications are;

1. The relationship between time management and motivation for university library librarians has significant implications. Despite the low positive relationship between motivation and time management, librarians' time management skills can improve with even a little increase in motivation. Motivated workers are more focused and organised, improving service delivery and performance. Since motivation is linked with time management, increasing staff motivation through recognition, financial incentives, and professional development will indirectly enhance librarians' time management. Therefore, Library administrators and managers can

enhance service delivery, productivity, and employee satisfaction by creating a motivating workplace.

2. The findings on job stress and time management in South-South Nigerian university libraries are essential. The significant negative correlation coefficient between job stress and time management shows that librarians' time management worsens when stress increases, and vice versa. Job stress will likely seriously hinder librarians' time management for service delivery. This emphasises the need to resolve job-related stress to improve librarian time management. It suggests that stress management programmes, work-life balance, and proper support mechanisms are necessary to optimise time management and improve university library service delivery. These findings also highlight the need for library administrators and managers to recognise and address the impact of job stress on librarians' time management to create a healthier and more productive workplace.

Recommendations

The following are recommended.

1. It has been established that staff motivation improves time management. Thus, library heads, LRCN, and NLA should organise recognition for librarians who deliver excellent service. Professional growth is also needed to enhance motivation. These measures can boost librarians' service delivery and performance.
2. Librarians should get free, and ongoing training from the NLA and LRCN. These training sessions should cover best

practices for time management and give librarians the tools they need to manage their work load more effectively.

3. Job stress management programs are needed. The library management and librarians should identify job-related stressors and provide stress management training and tools to help employees cope. Librarians must learn how to balance their family life and work. They need flexible work arrangements and a healthy workplace as it could minimise job stress and enhance time management. NLA and LRCN should organise free and continuous training for librarians. This is because training programmes and workshops on time management best practices can help staff enhance their skills and efficiency.

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